

Representation of performance and expressive meanings in *Mantra* for two pianos and live electronics by Karlheinz Stockhausen

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Abstract

Mantra for two pianos and live electronics is an example of application of a new compositional method, called by Stockhausen ‘Formel Komposition’. The piece includes a particular instrumentation (cymbales antiques and wood blocks) and a live sound processing of piano sounds. It is, according to the composer, related to the creation of a new idea of ‘symbiotic’ and ‘utopian’ composition. It is also a very structured composition based on the rules of a new compositional method.

The different aesthetic interpretations of the piece in the context of theoretical studies suggest different outcome in the performances. These can be related to the aesthetic points of view studied in the musicological field. My analysis starts from this assumption and examines some recorded fragments of different performances compared by listening and by signal analysis.

1. The compositional method

1.1. Main principles of the ‘Formel Komposition’

The formula is a basic structure in which all the components of a composition must be contained: pitches, durations, silences and so on. In the ‘Formel Komposition’ we have a set of rules, but also a marge of freedom in their application:

“You are probably familiar with the idea of formula in mathematics or chemistry. Since the composition *Mantra* in 1970 I use the idea of formula both in sense of a mathematical formula from which a world from relationships can be deduced, as well in sense of a magic formula with which it is possible to evolve marvelous events.”

(Stockhausen, 2003)

One of the key points of the formula concerning pitches is to use all the 12 pitches of the chromatic scale avoiding repetitions, but in a free way without the restrictions imposed for instance by the dodecaphonic technique. Above all, the variety in the use of the sound parameters is important. A suggestion of the composer is to focus on proportional relationship

and numerical series in particular regarding to build the rhythmic structures. Some of the main rules of the ‘Formel –Komposition’ may be summarized in few short principles, for instance, to use different elements, to grouping notes and silences with a different length, to alternate silences and sounds with great variety and to use numeric progressions to build relationships and proportions between all the elements of the composition.

1.2. The Formula of *Mantra*

Mantra’s formula, is based on 4 elements, and 13 pitches. A characteristic of this particular formula is his mirror form. The upper part of the first element mirrors the lower part of the second one. The lower part of the second element mirrors the upper of the first one and so on. In the table are summarizes the characters belonging to the elements of the *Mantra*’s formula: pitch number, duration and duration of silences in the four elements. The variety of this structure is given by the different number of sounds for each element, by their different duration and by the different length of the pause between one element and another.

Element	Pitch number	duration	Duration of silences
Element 1	4	10/4	6/4
Element 2	2	6/4	2/4
Element 3	4	15/4	1/4
Element 4	3	12/4	4/4

Example. 1: Composition of the formula of *Mantra*

Each of the 13 pitches composing the formula has a specific feature. The first pitch is characterized by a regular repetition, the second one by an accent at the end of the sound, the third is a normal sound and so on. The whole piece is based on the 13 pitches and composed by 13 cycles (one for each pitch). Each cycle is centered on one of the 13 pitches and is related to the pitches characteristic as explained by the composer:

“the work arises entirely from a 13 note formula, the mantra. There is nothing but continual series of this mantra and superimpositions of itself, in 12 forms of expansion and 13x12 transpositions. That is, in each of of the 13 large cycles- in each of wich a note of the mantra is itself the central note around wich the expanded form arise- a different one of the 13 mantric characteristics predominates.” (K. Stockhausen, 1991)

Starting from these elements (structure of the formula and pitches with specific features), all the piece is the result of transpositions and expansions of the elements of the *Mantra*. The composer points out that the procedures adopted in the composition of *Mantra* are exclusively transpositions and expansion of materials and the piece cannot be considered a variation form.

“*MANTRA*, therefore is not a variation form. Nothing of *Mantra* is varied, not a single note is added, nothing is “accompanied”, ornamented etc. The *Mantra* always stays itself and appears twelvefold, with its 13 characteristics¹. (Stockhausen, 1991)

1.3. The technology in *Mantra*

Besides to the rules of the ‘Formel Komposition’ in *Mantra* the signal processing plays an important compositional role. The live electronic technique of ring modulation is used in *Mantra* to realize a particular effect obtained by multiplying the piano’s sounds for given frequencies. Each expansion of the *Mantra*’s macroform is related with one of the 13 frequencies of the *Mantra*’s main sounds. Function of technology in *Mantra* is double, a timbral one, and a structural one. The timbral role consists in the particular effect of piano’s frequencies multiplication. The structural one consists in the subdivision of the piece in 13 different expansions, defined from the changing of frequency in the ring modulation.

“So called ring modulation, which I have employed as a technical process, makes possible a new system of harmonic relationships. To this end, each of the pianists has an apparatus at his left into which a microphone amplifier, a compressor, a filter, a ring modulator, a scaled sine-wave generator, and a volume control has been built. The piano sounds are amplified by 2 microphones, and ring-modulated by sine-waves. Behind each piano stand loudspeakers which project the modulated sound simultaneously with the played sound.” Depending on the intervallic distance of the other mantra pitches from the “mirror pitch” of the ring modulator, the modulated notes sound more or less “dissonant” and have spectra unlike the piano. Hence one perceives a continual “respiration” from consonant to dissonant, to consonant modulator sounds, resulting from the precisely tuned relationships between the modulating sine tones and the modulated piano notes. (Stockhausen, 1991)

2. Aesthetic implications

Mantra is a composition that has aroused great interest from musicologists. It marked a turning point in the composer's thought. Starting from it and up to the conclusion of the great cycle of *Licht*, Stockhausen will use the principles of the ‘Formel Komposition’. However the characteristics of this new technique have aesthetic implications that have given rise to different interpretations by musicologists. I will take into consideration in particular two points of view apparently very distant from each other: the interpretations by the musicologists Christoph von Blumröder and by Robin Maconie. Both date back to a period very close to the composition of *Mantra*. According with the point of view of Blumröder, *Mantra* should be the beginning of a ‘symbiotic composition’ in which different cultures merge with the utopian vision of the composer.

² Karlheinz Stockhausen, *Texte zur Musik*, 1970.1977, Du Mont, Köln 1978.

“In the develop and composition process of *Mantra* shows an aspect that can be seen as the first sign of the symbiotic character of this composition.....The symbiotic composition form is such an individual style, which arises from a utopian definition, without which recognition cannot exist today and the aim is to demand tendencies that this utopia should once prove to be a reality... Stockhausen talk about a ‘new folklore’ from which a symbiosis of different cultures and musical traditions is obtained”(Blumröder, 1976).

We can therefore affirm that Blumröder's point of view mainly highlights the symbiotic and utopian aspects of *Mantra* or the distance from the rigidity of the compositional process towards the integration of this with the suggestion of immersing oneself in the repetition of the sound structures according to a utopian principle of coexistence of the western and eastern tradition. If Blumröder's vision underlines the symbiotic aspect of *Mantra*, moreover pursued by the composer himself, on the contrary the musicologist Robert Maconie expresses a different point of view. In his opinion *Mantra* stands in contrast to the previous compositions as a piece ‘objective, active and synthetic.

“There is a coolness and reserve in the composer’s return ti the neutral sonority of the piano, to the world of equal temperament and to a rigorously conventional notation, using verbal not metronomic tempo indications, including graces notes but no ‘irrational’ note values (i.e. triplet, quintolet etc.)” (Maconie,1976).

Maconie above all, notes the precision character of the compositional structure and identifies in the piano an instrument that characterizes western culture and the tradition that led to the establishment of the temperate system. As can be seen therefore, Maconie unlike Blumröder, highlights the element of structural and compositional precision with respect to the philosophical aspects present in *Mantra*. The idea of precision and rigor is also underlined with regard to macro structure and the use of live sound processing:

“Structurally the work returns to the crystalline idea of the fifties, according to which every aspects of a work’s form from the smallest detail to the overall shape, ought to be derivable from one basic serial configuration.....*Mantra* considers the deeper issue of establishing a viable continuity between instrumental and electronic sound.”(Maconie, 1976)

Maconie highlights the interaction with technology as another element of precision and rigor:

“The music follows no programme, but may reasonably be described as a trip into an expanded word of sound, systematically exploring a cycle of harmonic spectra through which the piano timbre is electronically refracted. The mantra or basic formula is a pattern of notes inflections and intensities by which this exploration process is regulated”.(Maconie, 1976, p. 285)

These aesthetic perspectives highlight two different aspects of the composition that coexist. Their interest lies above all in the fact that each of these can lead to a different performance approach. In fact, privileging a symbiotic vision over understanding *Mantra* as a return to the rational vision of the temperate system can affect the result of a performance. In performances can be expressed an aesthetic perspective as I will try to explain through some examples.

3. Performance analysis

Some fragments from two rather different recorded performances will take into consideration to look for the connection with different aesthetic interpretations. The first performance considered is that by the duo Kontarsky recorded and published by the Stockhausen Verlag in 1991 on the CD No.16. It seems to take on an 'objective' vision of the piece in which the performance times are according to the composer's indications on the score. The characteristic of the piano as a percussive instrument is emphasized.

The second one is a live recording made in Milano, September 2008 by Bruno Canino and Antonio Ballista in a concert of the 'Festival Mito'. That performance proposes slowed-down times and an emphasis on the dynamics and resonances obtained with the fusion of electronic sounds and piano sound suggesting the idea of a timbre close to the concept of 'symbiotic composition'. The first version accredited by Stockhausen himself, the second one made independently of its supervision, are two examples quite distant in time and for this reason I think to be significant for my research. The purpose of the research is based on the assumption that the aesthetic perspective proposed by Blumröder agrees with the interpretation of the duo Canino and Ballista, while that of Maconie is rather reflected in the performance of the duo Kontarsky.

3.1. *Mantra*'s exposition

The piece starts with a presentation in four chords of the 13 pitches of the formula followed by the exposition of the main formula by the first piano. Stockhausen wants to briefly present all the pitches composing the formula and the formula itself. (measures 1-12) In the first 12 measures the Kontarsky duo overall performance time is 1minute and 25 seconds, instead the Canino and Ballista one is 1minute and 48 seconds. Furthermore Canino and Ballista emphasise the distance between the third and fourth chord in the measure 1 and the dynamics in the measures 3 and 4. They also begin with the repeated sound characteristic of the first expansion before to have finished to play the entire formula as indicated in the score.

Performance	Measures	Time	Characters
Canino - Ballista	1-12	1' 48''	Symbiotic
Kontarsky	1-12	1' 25''	Objective

Example. 2: performance time and character (mm.1-12)

In the two following examples is showed the onset time of measures 1-12 analysed with the software Sonic Visualizer. The exposition of the first four chord representing the summary of

the pitches of the formula are played more regularly by the duo Kontarsky, instead in the performance of Canino and Ballista there is a longer interval between the third and fourth chord.

Exp. Mm 1-2	Onset time Kontarsky	Onset time Canino-Ballista
Chord 1	0.899	0.969
Chord 2	1.465	1.248
Chord 3	2.023	1.979
Chord 4	2.2626	2.734

Example 3: Summary of onset time of Measures 1-2 in the Kontarsky and Canino-Ballista performances analysed with Sonic Visualiser

3.2. The First Expansion

The first expansion of *Mantra* starts at measure 12 until to measure 60.

It is characterized by the element of ‘regular repetition’, the connotation of the first pitch of the *Mantra*. We can recognize in the first expansion three structural levels: the first level is characterized by the expansion in time of the main pitches composing the four elements of the formula, the second one is represented by the ‘regular repetition’ of the pitch A and the third one is represented by the expansion and transposition of the single pitches, intervals and fragments of the formula.

In the performance of Canino and Ballista the first expansion is connected strictly with the exposition of the formula because as we noticed before, the ‘regular repetition’, character of the first pitch and consequently of the first expansion, begins on the fourth element of the formula (measure 7). Instead in the score respected in the performance of the duo Kontarsky the regular repetition begins on the first expansion with more distinction of the two sections

(measure 12). Canino and Ballista give more relevance to the regular repetition (second level), the Kontarsky duo to the different elements of the formula (first and third level).

Considering the duration of the expansion of the first element (m.12-20) in both performances we observe that the overall time is longer in the Kontarsky one.

First element- first expansion	Canino and Ballista performance	Kontarsky performance
mm.12-20	31 sec.	35 sec.

However, as happens for the beginning of the piece examined previously, when listening, it seems that the duration is longer in the performance of Canino and Ballista.

This happens because they perform the internal steps with greater freedom while keeping the overall time slightly faster. They also attach great importance to the repeated sound which constitutes what I have defined as level 2 much more than the duo Kontarsky does.

Regarding the dynamics analysed with Sonic Visualizer, we can observe that in the Kontarsky performance the start and end values are similar. During the performance the Kontarsky duo represented in the graph with the red line, play with more differentiated dynamics. The dynamics in the performance of the Canino and Ballista duo, represented in the graph with a blue line, are more discontinuous between the first and second value and then become more uniform in the other steps. That can be a reason for a perception of a longer time duration of the performance.

Example 5: dynamic's value of the performances of first element, first expansion

3.3. The final formula

The end of the composition is a repetition of the formula in a melodic form as a final summary of the materials used in the composition as well as the chords of the beginning.

Example 5: end of the composition (measures 884-887).

The two performances have also in this last fragment different overall duration: in the Kontarsky performance we have a duration of 1 minute and 18 seconds, instead in the Canino and Ballista only 58 seconds.

In the dynamic parameter in this case, the duo Kontarsky give less regularity instead Canino and Ballista. In particular approaching the end of the composition the duo Kontarsky emphasize the last sounds with a great dynamic's differentiation. Canino and Ballista on the contrary maintain a regularity in the dynamics of this last fragment.

Example 6: dynamic's values of the final exposition of the formula in both performa

4. Conclusions

From these first results of the analysis, we can conclude that the performance of the duo Kontarsky often has a longer overall duration and maintains in general a greater regularity in the general dynamics, but emphasizing some elements. On the contrary, the performance of the Canino and Ballista duo, often has a temporal concentration which, however, is not perceived when listening. That happens because they make longer time intervals within the single fragments. Sometimes as in the initial fragment, there are time dilations between the second and third chords for example, even if the overall time is less. In dynamics there is in general a greater global regularity in the duo Kontarsky performance with emphasis in some points. This

performance follows more closely the indications of the composer. Canino and Ballista applies a more contrasting dynamic from the beginning to the end of the analysed fragments and maintain a regularity inside the fragment. They give more relevance to different elements than the Kontarsky does, for example the level 2 of repeated sound in the first expansion of the formula. The meaning of these differences could be a different interpretation of the piece from an aesthetic point of view. In the performance of the duo Kontarsky there is a regularity and attention to the indications of the composer that refer to the Maconie's aesthetic interpretation related to a rigorous compositional method. In fact, the differentiation of the sections, the clarity of the performance and the observation of the dynamics corresponds to the idea of a return to the precision of western tradition recalled by Maconie. The performance of Canino and Ballista, on the other hand, is an example of greater freedom both in some temporal expansions, and in the dynamics and in some choices. This performance corresponds to the aesthetic idea of a symbiosis of different traditions referred to Blumröder's aesthetic interpretation. The examples discussed here would confirm the hypothesis. The future work will be to demonstrate its validity with further examples. In order to be able to affirm with greater certainty that the aesthetic vision of a piece can affect their performance and that therefore the analysis can be aimed at it in the case of *Mantra* it is necessary to extend the experience proposed in this article to other fragments and even to other performances.

5. References

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